

Table 2. Panicles/hill, panicle exertion, 1000-grain weight, and plant height of ratoon and main crops of some rice hybrids. Sukamandi, Indonesia, 1988-89 wet season.*

Hybrid, check	Panicles/hill (no.)		Panicle exertion (%)		1000-grain weight (g)		Plant height (cm)	
	Main	Ratoon	Main	Ratoon	Main	Ratoon	Main	Ratoon
V20 A/IR25912	13.5	10.00 (74)	104.05	77.65 (74)	26.13	20.07 (76)	116.0	68.6 (59)
V20 A/IR46	13.3	11.95 (89)	105.35	77.03 (73)	22.35	20.42 (92)	104.2	66.6 (64)
V20 A/IR64	12.5	9.35 (74)	105.70	85.79 (81)	28.10	20.34 (73)	111.6	71.7 (64)
V20 A/Kr. Aceh	16.4	11.25 (68)	93.00	86.99 (93)	29.15	22.64 (78)	116.6	73.5 (63)
V20 A/IR28178	13.1	8.80 (67)	109.51	80.83 (73)	26.05	20.24 (78)	113.5	64.7 (57)
V20 A/M66b	14.9	10.50 (70)	111.20	78.33 (70)	28.05	21.07 (76)	118.4	71.0 (60)
Dodokan	15.7	10.45 (66)	113.50	71.35 (63)	28.55	23.25 (82)	104.2	72.2 (69)
LSD (0.05)	3.6	3.81	7.55	2.98	5.66	6.58	3.7	3.6
CV (%)	10.4	14.7	2.9	1.5	8.7	12.9	1.3	2.1

*Figures in parentheses are % of main crop.

weight of the ratoon crop was about 76-78% of that of the main crop. Plant height ranged from 64.7 cm for V20 A/IR28178 to 73.5 cm for V20 A/Krueng-Aceh (Table 2). *Helminthosporium sigmoideum*

incidence on the hybrids was 6-50%, while that on Dodokan was only 1%. V20 A/IR25912, V20 A/IR64, and V20 A/IR28178 yielded significantly more than the check.

F₁ hybrids offer some advantages for use in the ratoon crop. In breeding programs for hybrid rice, emphasis should be given to selecting parents with good ratooning ability. ■

Yield and yield components of some new rice hybrids derived from IR58025 A and IR62829 A in Indonesia

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We evaluated 15 IRRI rice hybrids of which eight were derived from IR58025 A and seven from IR62829 A, three Indonesian hybrids derived from IR62829 A, IR64, and Way-Seputih in a yield trial during the 1991 dry season in Kuningan. Single seedlings were transplanted at 20- × 20-cm spacing in 3- × 5-m² plots with three replications. Plots

were fertilized with 135-50-50 kg NPK/ha. IR58025 A/IR10198, IR58025 A/IR15324, and IR58025 A/Pusa 150 yielded as much as IR64 and Way-Seputih. The hybrids had more unfilled grains/panicle than IR64 (see table). ■

Yield components of some new rice hybrids. Kuningan, Indonesia, 1991 dry season.

Hybrid, variety	Yield (t/ha)	Maturity (d)	1000-grain wt (g)	Filled grains/panicle (no.)	Panicles/hill (no.)	Panicle length (cm)	Plant height (cm)	Unfilled grains/panicle (no.)
IR64	5.9	135	20.41	61.11	16.9	19.8	68.9	13.42
IR58025 A/IR10198	5.9	136	21.59	81.28	16.23	20.6	77.7	24.20
IR58025 A/IR15324	5.4	127	22.61	74.33	14.96	20.3	77.1	24.81
Way-Seputih	5.2	136	22.62	88.34	12.53	16.9	77.4	24.13
IR58025 A/Pusa 150	5.2	130	21.40	79.04	15.43	18.2	74.8	36.57
IR58025 A/IR40750	5.0	141	20.24	79.97	14.9	18.2	81.3	45.46
IR62829 A/Pusa 150	4.9	127	19.43	44.19	19.4	16.6	66.0	23.5
IR58025 A/IR37839	4.7	136	21.34	63.14	16.23	19.6	78.4	23.65
IR62829 A/IR28238	4.7	127	18.02	71.18	15.2	16.5	73.9	32.70
IR62829 A/IR40750	4.5	130	19.11	46.70	19.93	17.9	67.8	28.29
IR58025 A/IR54742	4.4	143	21.92	75.90	11.23	20.4	86.0	54.15
IR62829 A/M66b	4.1	127	20.22	53.50	16.26	17.2	69.6	31.17
IR62829 A/IR15324	4.0	127	20.65	70.04	14.17	18.7	75.5	31.33
IR62829 A/IR10198	3.9	127	19.62	74.53	11.43	18.2	74.5	36.50
IR62829 A/IR54	3.4	136	21.31	39.49	19.7	18.2	67.8	32.0
IR62829 A/IR29723	1.8	130	21.50	26.02	17.13	16.0	68.4	64.55
IR62829 A/IR64	1.7	130	20.52	28.47	18.53	18.2	67.4	39.80
IR58025 A/IR29723	1.6	141	23.74	45.58	13.4	18.6	75.9	74.95
IR58025 A/IR32809	1.1	136	23.78	68.49	13.13	18.8	74.2	57.6
IR62829 A/IR32809	1.0	130	22.98	25.38	17.36	18.3	62.7	44.03
CV (%)	14.0	-	3.8	20.0	16.9	8.5	3.4	26.9
LSD (0.05)	0.9	-	1.29	15.38	4.28	2.52	4.08	16.13

An innovative approach to improve rice yield

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In areas where rice production has stagnated and demand continues to increase, new approaches are needed to stimulate production. We applied plant growth regulators (PGRs) to rice in an attempt to improve yield.

The 100-m² experimental and control plots had thirty 10-m rows with 0.2-m spacing between rows and 1-m spacing between plots, replicated three times. High-yielding PR106 seeds, treated with streptomycin and methoxy-ethyl-mercury chloride, were sown in mid-May and transplanted in late Jun. The foliar sprays of PGRs (Table 1) were applied weekly from early Aug to Oct using the manufacturers' recommended dose. The control plot was sprayed weekly with quantities of water equivalent to the recommended doses.

The chlorophyll content, plant height, and biomass were measured. Rice was harvested at maturity, and its yield recorded (Table 1), and characteristics analyzed (Table 2).

Spraying with PGRs promoted rice yield. The percent increase in the yield over control showed that PGR-H, CSL, and Aminos gave comparable bioefficacy.

PGRs Vipul, Paras, and 110-R are classified as long-chain aliphatic alcohols; CSL, Aminos, and PGR-H as modified amino acids. A correlation between these characteristics and bioefficacy suggests that the latter PGRs promote larger biomass and more chlorophyll, which lead to efficient photosynthesis and higher productivity.

The number of sprays (nine) used in the experiment was high to establish the utility of PGRs; dose and frequency of spraying still need to be optimized.

Rice from higher yielding PGRs was analyzed for nutritional and commercial characteristics (Table 2). Most of the nutritional characteristics were comparable, except for an increase in protein content, which is highly desirable. Reduced breakability during polishing

Table 1. Chlorophyll content, leaf dry weight, plant height, and yield profiles of rice sprayed with various PGRs, Patiala, India.^a

Plant growth regulator	Chlorophyll		Dry leaves		Height		Yield		
	mg/g	±SD	g	±SD	cm	±SD	kg	±SD	Increase (%) over control
PGR-H	1.55	0.04	1.19	0.03	112	4.0	25.4	2.4	41
CSL	1.34	0.05	1.11	0.05	103	3.0	25.1	1.7	39
Aminos	1.32	0.05	1.12	0.04	106	4.7	24.5	2.0	36
Vipul	1.17	0.03	1.02	0.05	98	8.3	24.0	3.3	33
110-R	1.22	0.01	1.04	0.01	100	6.3	21.0	1.8	17
Paras	1.18	0.01	1.04	0.00	102	2.3	20.4	2.3	13
Control	1.10	0.02	1.01	0.03	98	6.2	18.0	3.2	-

^aData from 30 samples (10/plot).

Table 2. Nutritional and commercial characteristics of rice grain.

Plant growth regulator	Characteristic (%)						
	N	Protein	Minerals	Moisture	Water ^a	Germination	Breakables
PGR-H	1.3	8.1	0.4	9.2	4.0	92	17
CSL	1.4	8.8	0.5	9.8	4.2	92	25
Aminos	1.3	8.1	0.5	9.3	4.3	93	21
Control	1.1	6.9	0.5	9.2	3.9	89	17

^aEstimated as residual dry weight after soaking 100 g in 500 ml demineralized water for 16 h at ambient temperature.

also has commercial significance.

Large-scale PGR spray trials in various agroclimatic zones and using

different rice varieties are suggested to establish PGR utility for increasing rice production. ■

A path coefficient analysis of rice panicle traits

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We evaluated the effects of panicle characters on grain yield in 20 high-yielding genotypes during rabi (Sep-Jan) 1991-92. We planted the genotypes in three rows of 10 plants each at 20- × 10-cm spacing in a randomized block design with three replications. Panicle

traits and grain yield were recorded for the main tillers of 10 randomly selected plants for each entry in each replication. We used path coefficient analysis to assess the direct and indirect influence of various panicle characters on grain yield.

Direct (underlined) and indirect effects of panicle traits on grain yield in rice^a, Tamil Nadu, India, 1991-92 rabi.

Character	Panicle length	No. of primaries	No. of secondaries	Primary length	Secondary length	Filled grains/primary	Filled grains/secondary	Chaffy grains/primary	Chaffy grains/secondary	Total filled grains	Total chaffy grains	Genotypic correlation with yield
Panicle length	<u>-0.263</u>	-0.137	-0.492	0.285	0.074	-0.252	0.156	-0.054	-0.245	1.828	-0.176	0.724**
No. of primaries	-0.146	<u>-0.246</u>	-0.483	0.118	0.009	0.175	0.212	-0.087	-0.166	1.469	-0.350	0.505*
No. of secondaries	-0.193	-0.177	<u>-0.671</u>	0.252	0.036	-0.214	0.264	-0.105	-0.404	2.082	-0.107	0.763**
Primary length	-0.213	-0.083	-0.481	<u>0.351</u>	0.083	-0.409	0.100	0.016	-0.204	1.858	-0.232	0.787**
Secondary length	-0.129	-0.015	-0.160	0.194	<u>0.150</u>	-0.223	-0.016	-0.066	-0.187	0.757	0.141	0.445*
Filled grains/primary	-0.107	0.070	-0.232	0.232	0.054	<u>-0.618</u>	-0.059	-0.007	-0.260	1.250	0.207	0.530*
Filled grains/secondary	0.108	0.137	0.467	-0.093	0.006	-0.097	<u>-0.380</u>	0.071	0.276	-0.844	0.087	-0.261
Chaffy grains/primary	0.031	0.046	0.152	0.012	-0.022	0.010	-0.059	<u>-0.463</u>	0.760	-0.464	-1.220	-0.291
Chaffy grains/secondary	0.078	0.049	0.327	-0.087	-0.034	0.194	-0.126	0.425	<u>0.829</u>	-1.020	-1.136	-0.502*
Total filled grains	-0.210	-0.158	-0.611	0.286	0.050	-0.338	0.140	-0.094	-0.370	<u>2.284</u>	-0.103	0.875**
Total chaffy grains	-0.034	-0.063	-0.053	0.060	-0.015	0.094	0.024	0.412	0.687	0.171	<u>-1.370</u>	-0.087

*, ** = significant at 5 and 1% levels, respectively.